

Understanding the Mental Well-Being of Teachers in a Workplace Through Support System: Secondary Teachers in Focus

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Abstract. This study explored and investigated the experiences and perspectives of public-school teachers, mainly in understanding their mental wellness. The study aims to identify the teachers' strengths and weaknesses as well as the educational insights regarding the support system. The researcher collected data from 10 public secondary teachers with at least three years in service and teaching at Matina District, Division of Davao City, chosen based on their experiences, particularly in experiencing mental health issues. Using the quantitative method of the study, results revealed the themes in teachers' lived experiences were improved teaching practice, providing a helping hand, and boosting student involvement. It also advances improved teaching practice, provides a helping hand, and boosts student involvement. However, besides strengths, the participants also underpinned some weaknesses, such as the dependence of the teachers on others. This study uncovered some insights: developing sincere connections and improved teaching practice. Teachers were also into this kind of system since they are ignited by the success of every bit of the educational field, not only for their future self-improvement but also for the eagerness of every student to engage more in learning. Lastly, the findings of this study would enable future researchers to facilitate research that would involve a support system for teachers to understand mental well-being and improve their teaching performances. This study would also serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

KEY WORDS

1. support system 2. mental well-being 3. secondary teachers

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Mental health is a fundamental human right and crucial to personal, community, and socio-economic development. And it is vital to every human being to possess this kind of health and support. It's inevitable to go through ups and downs in life. However, while we are going through a difficult period, we always try to reach out and grab hold of someone. Support can take many forms, including financial and emotional support. Having a support system has also been proven to reduce depression, anxiety, and reduce stress. In order for us to thrive, we need a support system to be there for us when we are in need. It may also come from a person's family, friends, or coworkers, as well as from a larger field or industry. So, having a variety of resources is incredibly useful, and that is what a support system is. Cherry (2018) argues

that a person's support system is their social network, which helps them cope with stress and frequently gives them the energy they need to succeed. This relationship is crucial to how you live your daily life, whether you want to spend time with the people you care about or are in a personal crisis and need instant aid. Dr. Sue (2016) further stated that having a support system can help people feel less depressed, anxious, and alone. The purpose of creating a network of support systems is to reduce stress. Numerous advantages of having a support system include a higher sense of well-being, improved coping skills, and a longer, healthier life (Cathy, 2014). However, among all professions, teaching is the most honorable.

Others agree, claiming that teaching is a well-paying career that helps develop a generation of knowledgeable workers and professionals. Education is a tool for changing people's lives. However, a teacher also faces numerous difficulties while instructing. According to Tustin (2016), teaching, particularly for freshly employed teachers, will present a variety of challenges. There will always be tension and strain. Thus, one needs to create a support network at school to help them become well-rounded individuals with emotional and social skills to withstand this kind of predicament. About half of all mental illnesses, including anxiety, depression, severe emotional disorder, and attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder, are said to be one of the main mental health problems. Suicide is frequently the result of underlying mental health problems and is currently the second leading cause of death among Canadian youth. (Kirby Keon, 2006). Thus, there expressed the urgent need to take action to address the number of children and adolescents suffering from mental health issues. The teaching profession is related to various environmental challenges and potential stressors teachers face: incompletely regulated working hours, infinite teaching tasks, and the division of the work-

place between school and home. Moreover, the teaching profession is associated with low levels of control in regard to effects achieved, no career possibilities, and a lack of feedback on the long-term consequences of teaching at school (Ruthland, 2003). According to Stanley (2018), who wrote about the crisis in the support system, there were 35 percent more teachers seeking support from April 2017 to March 2018 than there were in the previous 12 months. According to the most recent results of the 2017 health survey, educational professionals reported feeling stressed out most of the time or constantly as a result of their work. Because of this, several highly qualified instructors frequently quit their jobs. The government's support for the public educational system in the Philippines has been dwindling. As a result, the Department of Education's 2006 budget is nearly 6 percent lower than the 2001 allotment. The significant shortages of instructors in the public education system result from falling education allocations. Furthermore, according to a study conducted by the Philippine National University (PNU) Academic Research and Development Center, the Philippines should increase its investment in teacher education, which is now among the lowest in Asia. According to the PNU report, the Philippines ranks second only to Cambodia regarding government support for education, with only 2.8 percent. This demonstrates that the lesser the government funding, the higher the percentage of teachers failing the license examination. Thus, the government has been pushed to provide more excellent assistance for teacher education to improve teaching performances and the country's general education quality. (Malipot, 2017).

1.1. Purpose of the Study—It was true that there was a need to place a more significant emphasis on the support system as a factor in the effectiveness of the instructional process and to improve teaching performance. Following that, this study was undertaken to investigate the

experiences and perspectives of public-school teachers, mainly in understanding their mental wellness, which is primarily a determinant for improving their teaching performances in the District of Matina Davao City. The collected data would investigate the effect of the support system on an understanding of the instructors' mental well-being based on live experiences and personal information. To clarify, this study was

based on the premise that it was the first of its kind and that no other study had been undertaken.

1.2. Research Questions—This study investigated and assessed teachers' experiences emphasizing mental health in the public school. It specifically tries to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers regarding the support system?
- (2) How do teachers describe the advantages and disadvantages of support systems in understanding mental well-being?
- (3) What educational insight can be drawn from the teachers in understanding mental well-being using a support system?

The preview of this study focuses on the beneficiaries of the following: The National Government should support vast opportunities in the educational sector, particularly the welfare of teachers, who are the key instrument and wheel of education in providing competent individuals to future generations. By emphasizing budget allocation and providing them with training, programs, and other significant experiences that would improve their teaching performances, the government should support vast opportunities in the educational sector. Instructors should actively cultivate relationships with other teachers and colleagues to stay engaged in studying their craft. This would also serve as a platform for practicing various skills and developing a support system, both essential for understanding mental well-being and improving teaching performances. Lastly, the findings of this study would enable future researchers to facilitate research that would involve a support system for teachers to understand mental well-being and improve their teaching performances. This study would also serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

1.3. Definition of Terms—The essential terms were describe operationally: Mental

Well-being: A state of well-being where individuals realize their potential, cope with normal life challenges, work productively, and contribute to their community. It encompasses emotional, psychological, and social well-being. **Support System:** A network of individuals or resources that provide emotional, practical, or informational assistance, helping individuals to cope with stress and improve their mental well-being. In the context of teachers, it includes peers, administrators, and institutional support that enhances their professional and personal lives. **Lived Experiences:** The personal knowledge and subjective experiences of teachers as they navigate through their professional and personal lives, particularly focusing on their mental health and well-being. **Teaching Performance:** The effectiveness and efficiency with which teachers deliver education, engage students, and manage classroom activities, often influenced by their mental well-being and the support they receive.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—

1.4.1. Teachers' Mental Well-being—Mental health is defined by the WHO (2005) as a state where individuals realize their potential, cope with normal life challenges, work productively, and contribute to their community. Men-

tal health issues among teachers have increased globally, becoming a major cause of impairment (WHO, 2003; WHO, 2013). Promoting mental wellness involves creating environments that support healthy lifestyles and emotional functioning (O'Reilly et al., 2018).

1.4.2. Support System—Support systems enhance human capabilities in thinking and problem-solving, involving tools and technologies in K–12 education (National Academy of Sciences, 2019). They include emotional and practical support from individuals like friends, family, and professionals (Kinnear, 2017; Williams, 2014). Support groups bring together people with similar experiences, providing emotional and practical benefits (Delisle et al., 2016; Mayo Clinic, 2018). Decision support systems aid in collaborative planning and effective decision-making (Klosterman, 1999; Barr et al., 1998). Social support from family, especially for the elderly, is crucial (Shanas, 1979).

1.4.3. Support System for Teachers—Teacher stress, affecting up to 25 percent of teachers, leads to burnout and high turnover, impacting student outcomes (Hanover Research, 2015). Support for teachers, especially new ones, through stress management programs and school psychologists is essential (Bullough, 2005; European Commission, 2013). Inclusive education is supported through legislative frameworks, adequate funding, and collaboration among stakeholders (Crawford, 2004). Beginning teacher support should include personal, emotional, and problem-focused support, as well as opportunities for critical self-reflection (Stansbury Zimmerman, 2000; Huffman Leak, 1986). Peer coaching improves teaching strategies and skills retention (Showers, 1985; Baker Showers, 1984).

1.4.4. Other Related Studies—Professional development programs that include support systems, like coaching, are more effective when teachers collaborate and receive consistent

support (DeMonte, 2013; Hatch et al., 2005). Time constraints and lack of commitment from teachers hinder the effectiveness of co-teaching (Jurkovsky Müller, 2018; Takala Wickman, 2018). Teacher quality significantly impacts student learning, and improving teacher recruitment, preparation, and professional development is crucial (Araujo et al., 2014; Archibald et al., 2011). Positive student-teacher relationships boost student motivation (Ryan Deci, 2009). Teacher collaboration, supported by school leaders, enhances student achievement and teacher performance (Killion, 2015).

Support systems, whether emotional, practical, or professional, play a crucial role in enhancing teachers' mental well-being, reducing stress, and improving educational outcomes. Effective collaboration, professional development, and a strong support network are key to fostering a positive teaching and learning environment.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study expands on the systems of care approach first proposed by Stroul and Friedman (1986), to address the needs of teachers with severe emotional disturbances is a community-based and culturally sensitive healthcare model. system of care has been an improvement on previous health care models by including not only a continuum of services for teachers but also a philosophy of “mechanisms, arrangements, structures or processes to ensure that the services are provided in a coordinated, cohesive manner” (Stroul Friedman,). This approach calls for collaboration and integration of private and public mental health providers and services to ensure the complete mental health care system reaches all teachers rather than a select few (Center for School Mental Health Analysis and Action, 2007). This study expands on Kegan's (2010) constructive growth theory, which discusses how teachers are supported through systems in a school environment and how they enhance their teaching skills. According to con-

structive developmental theory, an individual's thinking can go through five phases throughout life. As a person advances to a more complicated stage, that person considerably enhances their ability to make sense of the world. Constructive development theory, as said, allows an individual to comprehend themselves and their world based on their surroundings, promoting growth throughout an individual's life span. While going through stages, employing others to help people grow and evolve throughout their adult life. An individual can advance from one stage to the next with an increased ability to make sense of life's obstacles. Based on his or her experiences, each individual can amass a more considerable complexity of learning (Kegan Lahey, 2010). The preceding critique and the alternative theory of public well-being proposed here respond to Huppert et al. (2004), who argue that current well-being theory fails to integrate neurobiology, psychology, and social science perspectives adequately. The approach to theory development adopted here is integrative, as Huppert et al. suggest. Much of the evidence and some of the conceptual thinking already exists (in various places) to constitute the proposed theory but has not been brought together in a coherent whole. The theory can also support the idea that utilizing the support systems provided by the school would assist them in growing in the profession and lead them to become effective educators. The above-stated thoughts were a catalyst to guide this study. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected variables. The experiences in development of a support system for teachers to understand their mental

well-being and improve their teaching performances in public school would be a fantastic experience for those teachers to grow and update their skills. There is an existing concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines the advantages and disadvantages of the support system in understanding the mental well-being of the teachers, and the last circle incorporates the insights of the teachers. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected variables. the experiences teachers' experiences on the support system in understanding mental well-being, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers, and learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on personal health development and engagement that would promote mental health and development. It was an integral component of health and well-being that underpins our individual and collective abilities to make decisions, build relationships, and shape our world. Mental health as a basic human right. Moreover, it was crucial to personal, community, and socio-economic development. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of exploring the experiences of teachers in mental health development in trying times, a way of teaching and learning development that was very critical to school success. Teachers describe the advantages and disadvantages of support systems in understanding mental well-being and developing a familiar intersection. The insights that can be drawn from the findings of the study.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It describes these assumptions and frames them into interpretive frameworks so it can understand their significance to our study. It established the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Philosophical assumptions have a variety of types and are elaborated below. Ontology, or the nature of reality, relates to reality and its characteristics. By exploring complex forms of evidence from different persons' experiences and insights, researchers encompassed the idea of multiple realities and reported on these multiple realities. This part of the research examines how it relates to the nature of reality. Moreover, it was a branch of metaphysics concerned with identifying existing things (Carnaghan, 2019). According to Creswell (2012), reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. It was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. Thus, multiple realities exist, including those of the researcher, the individuals who investigated, and the readers or audiences interpreting the study. In this research, through extensive quotes and themes that reflect the words and provide evidence of different perspectives, the researcher was anchored on the participants' interpretations, perceptions, and voices to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed. Moreover, to ensure the reliability of the results, the researcher would ensure that the respondents' responses were thoroughly coded. Thus, the researcher would avoid making personal bias as the study progresses and underpin the genuineness and thoughtfulness of the responses. Epistemology. Researchers would try to get as close as possible to the study participants. Subjective evidence was assembled based on individual views from research conducted in the field. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information (Carnaghan, 2019). Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), added that the researcher

should close the distance from the participants as this would create collaboration, become an insider, and spend time in the field with the participants. To obtain direct information that would provide evidence to the knowledge of the study, the researcher would ensure that close interaction with the participants is built. Researchers make their values known in the study and actively report their values and biases and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation (Carnaghan, 2019). It was, therefore, also called the theory of value, the philosophical study of goodness or value in the broadest sense of these terms. The researcher would understand the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher would preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. This is to uphold the dignity and value of every detail of the information obtained from the participants. Rhetoric means reporting what reality was through the eyes of my research participants. This was very important because it means that the researcher reported objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The researcher would also use personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Furthermore, in this study, the researcher would implement the qualitative research method of phenomenology, which would allow the exploration of teachers' understanding and practices regarding the development of collaborative support systems and open up different feelings and insights into their experiences. According to Koppa et. al. (2010), Phenomenological research enables the exploration of experiences and different abstract

perceptions or the sensory perceptions of the research phenomenon as well as the form of understanding based on these experiences and insights. Therefore, the study's strategy was based on your or other people's experiences and sensory perceptions. In order to produce in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon, the study aims to describe and analyze the phenomenon by using other people's experiences. The goal of this research would work well with the definition in trying to understand the exploration of the understanding and practices of teachers on the development of collaborative support systems. The phenomenological researchers investigated teachers' lived experiences to find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experiences it and to describe the phenomenon through the composite narrative.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, Phenomenological research was concerned with studying experiences from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasizes the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was decisive for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This research employed a qualitative research method that engaged a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Creswell (2013), as cited by Chambers (2013), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews

were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview attempts to answer questions like "What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? Or "What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon?" Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data is then read, reread, and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning. Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In addition, as cited by Chambers (2013), Maxwell (2013) also added that, with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology would attempt to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. Furthermore, qualitative research was mostly associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. It is a research method used extensively by scientists and researchers to study human behavior, opinions, themes, and motivations. Thus, qualitative data covered the features, attributes, and characteristics of a phenomenon that was interpreted thematically. It was also closely associated with survey design techniques, focus groups, individual case studies, and interviews (Wilson and Shuttleworth, 2008). As Lester (1999) posited, the phenomenological approach aims to illuminate and identify specific phenomena through how the actors perceive them. In the human sphere, this typically translates into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing them from the research participant's perspective. Phenomenology was concerned with studying experience from the individual's perspective, 'bracketing' taken-for-granted assumptions and usual ways of perceiving. Furthermore, the qualitative research mainly was associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. It is a research method used extensively by scientists and researchers to study human behavior, opinions, themes, and motivations. Qualitative data was mainly concerned with the phenomenon's features, attributes, and characteristics that could be interpreted thematically. Qualitative methods were often closely associated with survey design techniques, focus groups, individual case studies, and interviews (Wilson Shuttleworth, 2008). According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews would provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that qualitative research primarily uses interviews. They occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews could also help follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to explore the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). According to Quad (2016), the researcher would transcribe and type the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews are particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher then collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via extended interviews.

Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization that would extract significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience.

Several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher was required to have a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study should be individuals who have experienced the phenomenon. The researcher would need to bracket his/her experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her observations were incorporated into the study. The phenomenological approaches would be based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, emphasizing the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since this study focuses on exploring and assessing the teachers' experience and feelings towards the collaborative support system focusing on the teachers, the researcher intends to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative research method.

2.4. Research Participants—This study aimed the researcher to make an exploration, particularly in understanding the mental well-being of teachers in a workplace by means of

a support system. The researcher collected data from 10 public secondary teachers with at least three years in the service and teaching at Matina District, Division of Davao City, who were chosen based on their experiences, particularly in experiencing mental health issues. The researcher desired an extensive gathering of ideas from the key informants. The purposive sampling was used in this study. The researcher chose purposive sampling to ensure that the informants were reliable and knowledgeable and had much experience on the research topic. Further, purposive sampling also guarantees the quality of data collected and adequate information. All interviews were tape-recorded and transcribed verbatim afterward, as this would protect against bias and provide a permanent record of what was and was not said. It was also helpful to make 'field notes' during and immediately after each interview about observations, thoughts, and ideas about the interview, as this would help in the data analysis process. A good quality multi-directional external microphone was used to record focus groups, as internal microphones were useful to cope with the variation in volume of different speakers. If observers were present, they were introduced to the participants as someone who was just there to observe and often also would take notes. Videotaping required more than one camera to capture the whole group, as well as additional operational personnel in the room (Chadwick, et. al., 2008).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethics was described as the branch of philosophy that deals with decision-making dynamics concerning right and wrong. Scientific research, like all human activities, is governed by individual, community, and social values. Research ethics involve requirements for daily work, protecting subjects' dignity, and publishing information in the research (Fouka and Mantzorou, 2011). Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher

needs to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participants in this field. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most essential parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Informed Consent. The Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to in the conduct and practice of this study. The invitation to the participants ensures that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants are expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assures them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Social Value. The research was essential to the society. In this study, the social value focuses on the experience of teachers.

This study was specifically conducted among elementary teachers. This study also serves as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was the challenges the teachers face in using interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there was no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any type of misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they are not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher has to ensure that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent

to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The study results were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information was available and was placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers are aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview was carried out. This allows the participants to amend or remove any information they feel might identify them. The researcher reserves the right to employ pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensures that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem should ensure that the study is completed. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher should strive to ensure that the study could be completed successfully

in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helps enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensures that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study hoped to be completed in the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study does not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher expresses great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respects other works by properly citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also uses quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assures that honesty is present in working the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and or results is included, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.6. Roles of the Researcher—The researcher is responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks

help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were correctly secured as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study are presented through research questions – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for the improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—In gathering information, the researcher personally conducted in-depth interviews with participants and saturated the information through one-on-one in-

terviews. Interviewing refers to structured or unstructured verbal communication between the researcher and the participants. The interview was conducted in a conducive, quiet environment, meaning it was free from disturbance and the participants felt safe. The interview was initiated individually for about 30 to 40 minutes. In light of the principles of decorum and standards, the researcher adheres to the following steps in the conduct of the interview and focus group discussion and that was first, make an appointment with the participants, second, prepare a quiet room conducive to conversation, third was arranged chairs to enhance a face-to-face interviewing, next was to prepare a voice recorder, and lastly, to provide a jar of water. Before the interview, the researcher thanked the participants for their time and willingness to take part in the study. The researcher reminded the participants of the agreement and explained that the interview was unstructured and that the information given by the participants determined probing questions. The researcher secured the permission of the participants to record the interview (Talbot, 2005). Furthermore, interviews also have strengths and weaknesses. The strength of an interview was that the interviews provided helpful information when participants could not be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They could also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions encourage unbiased and truthful answers. However, the weaknesses include that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer interprets the information. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that pleases the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require a high level of technical competence to be used. It could also be time-consuming, and inexperienced interviewers may not be able

to keep the questions properly focused (Quad, 2016). Other than that, the researcher also stimulated conversations and reactions through the focus group discussion since focus groups may share many common features with less structured interviews. However, there was more to them than merely collecting similar data from many participants at once. A focus group was a group discussion on a particular topic organized for research purposes (Chadwick et al., 2008). Thematic Content Analysis. Anderson (1998) defines thematic content analysis (TCA) as a descriptive presentation of qualitative data. Interview transcripts from research participants or other identifiable writings that reflect experientially on the topic of investigation are examples of qualitative data. Textural data may be accompanied by video, image, or other types of data; however, this explanation of Thematic Content Analysis is limited to textual data. By detecting similar themes in the texts presented for analysis, thematic content analysis depicts the thematic content of interview transcripts. It was the most fundamental of qualitative analytic processes, and it informs all qualitative analytic procedures and, in some way, informs all qualitative methods. The researcher's epistemological perspective was objective or objectivistic when conducting a Thematic Content Analysis. To express the communality of voices across participants, the researcher groups and distills a list of similar themes from the texts. Every reasonable effort is made to use labels for topics derived from participants' actual words and to group themes in a way that directly reflects the texts as a whole. While selecting and identifying themes does necessitate some interpretation, it was kept to a bare minimum. The researcher's personal views and thoughts about the themes, or the Thematic Content Analysis themes might mean, were essentially irrelevant to the Thematic Content Analysis (Anderson, 1998) also affirmed. In analyzing the data, the researcher adopted the steps utilized by An-

derson (1998). Before beginning a Thematic Content Analysis, the researcher made multiple copies of the interview transcript or other extant text, including post-interview notes as relevant and stipulated in the Methodology. Next, the researcher marked all descriptions relevant to the topic of inquiry with a Highlighter. From the highlighted areas, mark each distinct unit of meaning. This means that a break or change in meaning separates units. However, the researcher retained all information relevant to understanding a meaning unit within the meaning unit. Units may vary in text length. Labeled each pile as initial categories or themes using keywords or phrases copied from highlighted texts. Then, if obvious information was missing from the text, the researcher identifies categories that were missing and goes through the entire interview transcript, identifying distinct units, grouping and regrouping similar and dissimilar units, and re-labeling categories for each additional interview transcript (or other texts), use the Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) was indicated in the steps highlighted above. Afterward, when all Thematic Content Analysis is complete, the researcher reads each Thematic Content Analysis separately. While retaining meaning units, combined categories or themes for all interview transcripts and notes. Collapse or subdivide categories as appropriate. Re-label categories as appropriate. After a few days, the researcher reread the total categories. Whether too many or too few categories made overall sense of the interview transcripts given on the topic. Redo all the instructions above until the researcher was satisfied that the categories reflect the interview transcripts as a whole (Anderson, 1998). Environmental Triangulation. A significant humanistic, interactional, and empathic aspect characterizes qualitative research. This type of study focuses on a set of meanings, values, beliefs, and social behaviors that aren't easily quantified. Qualitative studies in the health field allow researchers to understand

the perspectives of users, professionals, and managers on a variety of issues impacting the services and treatment provided to experience health, illness, and death, among other situations (Minayo Guerriero, 2012). Ullrich et al. (2012) also added that due to the characteristics that underlie qualitative research, its scientific rigor was constantly questioned, which was linked to the criteria of reliability, validity, and generality used in its development. On the other hand, these objections are based on quantitative assumptions that do not correspond to the goals of qualitative research, which were to understand, analyze, and describe a specific occurrence rather than measure or quantify it. Moreover, Heale and Noble (2019) mentioned that triangulation is a technique for enhancing the credibility and validity of research findings in a research study. Validity was concerned with the extent to which a study accurately reflected or evaluated the notion or concepts being explored; credibility relates to trustworthiness and how convincing a study was. In a research project, triangulation could help ensure that fundamental biases stemming from using a single method or observer were overcome by mixing theories, methods, or observers. Environmental triangulation entails the utilization of multiple locations, settings, and other essential aspects connected to the study's environment, such as time, day, and season. The objective was to figure out whether environmental elements, if any, might impact the data collected throughout the study. Validity has been established if the results were consistent under different environmental situations. It was only used when it is likely that the findings may be influenced by environmental factors. Thus, the research was conducted at Daniel R. Aguinaldo National High School, Matina District, and Division of Davao City. The environment provided by the researcher to the participants facilitated a more significant space, the key information for the participants' experiences remained the same, and the only as-

pect that changed was the level of information, which, in turn, were evident with a greater or lesser extent under certain circumstances.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—The researcher applied qualitative analysis to establish the study's credibility, transferability, and dependability. The participants' experiences were collected and investigated through one-on-one non-structured interviews, audio tapes, field notes, and peer debriefing. The audio tape one-on-one, structured interview, peer debriefing, and field notes were performed within four days by participants, with each session lasting between 1 hour and 15 minutes. Interview Guide. The researcher prepared five open-ended questions in the unstructured interview to gather additional information and supporting answers to validate the study's findings. The interview questions were inclined to the components contained in the questionnaire. Unstructured interviews did not reflect preconceived theories or ideas and were performed with little or no organization. Their use would generally only be with significant depth, or virtually nothing was known about the subject area, or a different perspective of a known subject area is required. The purpose of the research interview was to explore individuals' views, experiences, beliefs, and/or motivations on specific matters. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, were believed to provide a deeper understanding of social phenomena than would be obtained from purely quantitative methods, such as questionnaires (Stewart et al., 2008). A questionnaire was a set of carefully designed, written down, and tested questions that were asked of individual respondents to gather information in research (Enon, 2008). The questionnaires were also an appropriate way to collect large amounts of data quickly. The open-ended questions allow the respondents to give further opinions by qualifying or substantiating their answers. They would also be intended to tap as much information as possible from the different categories of respondents.

O’Leary (2014) added that questionnaires most notably discover what the masses think. These include market research, political polling, customer service feedback, evaluations, opinion polls, and social science research.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on how it was being conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study was important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) stated that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was “how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study’s findings were applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” could mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizers as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students’ perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide a generalization of the study based on his own

context and can address the core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research was never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which required an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings were consistent and could be repeated. In this component, a database was significant in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was kept adequately for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that “how a study was conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques.”

2.10. *Framework Analysis*—In the conceptual framework of the study, it was shown that the experiences of teachers regarding the understanding of the mental well-being of the teachers in a workplace by means of a support system

were taken into account, unveiling and bringing out another hope and viewpoint to similar situations or cases. To bring out their insights and feelings and to make a difference in the educational system, the experiences of the teachers were analyzed. This aims to stipulate information and ideas on how the development of a collaborative support system for teachers affects the professional development of the teachers as well as in the higher context. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. The study, which involved semi-structured in-depth interviews with teachers, was conducted with a strong emphasis on ethical considerations. All teachers provided consent before participating, as shown in Figure 2. The data analysis process involved developing a list of significant statements from the transcripts and grouping them into larger units of information, known as meaning tunings or themes. The organized data were then collected, listened to, and recorded, following the ethical guidelines set forth by Creswell (2007). The researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions to remain true to the phenomenon with the list of non-redundant units of meaning. The researcher would also rigorously examine these

units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context (Groenewald, 2004). To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (cited in (Sanders, 2003; Speziale Carpenter, 2007)); Each transcript should be read and re-read to obtain a general sense of the whole content; significant statements about the phenomenon under study should be extracted from each transcript. These statements must be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their page and line numbers; meanings should be formulated from these significant statements, and the formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes; the findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study; the fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described. Finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher's descriptive results with their experiences. Lastly, the combined description of the phenomenon was written, this is the essence of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of the phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter encompasses the results generated from analyzing the interview data. The themes that emerged from the analysis were also presented. Together with the themes are answers that mainly discuss the objectives of the study, which contain inclusive discussions. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used to present the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. The Lived Experiences of Support System in Understanding Mental Health— Teachers have connections with other people, ranging from family, friends, co-workers, ac-

quaintances, and others. Regardless of what category they fit in, the people who provide positive support are the people who have a positive influence on your life because they are a part

Fig. 2. Illustrates the descriptive phenomenological data analysis process created by Colaizzi (1978)

of it. This is where the collaborative support pertains to. They are someone who becomes our helping hand and avenue to take us away from embroilment. Withal, others also believe that this makes us become effective, engaging and committed. The first aspiration of this study is to discover teachers’ live experiences regarding the support system. It sought participants’ personal, hands-on experiences on their views. The informants’ responses were grouped into themes. The informant’s first-hand accounts of teachers’ experiences with the support system were coded based on the information gathered during the interview, and the following themes emerged. Participants in this focus group discussion include the teachers and the stakeholders.

3.1.1. Improved Teaching techniques— Finding effective teaching strategies that would appeal to each student, who primarily tracks with diverse intellect, is one of the most difficult tasks every teacher wrestles with. So, in order to move forward with an effective teaching method, one must develop effective teaching techniques. In other words, the success of the teachers as they give their best effort de-

pends on the emphasis of the support system. As teachers receive support from other teachers, colleagues, administrators, and the government, effective teaching practices are essential to producing effective students. This is parallel to the statement of DeMonte, (2013) that Support systems, which are frequently included in professional development programs and are occasionally referred to as coaching, appear to complement other elements of professional development, according to the research that is currently available. It is more likely to be successful if it lasts longer, if instructors work together to share what they learn from coaching, and if they get to watch instruction and then discuss what they saw with a coach. This functionality depends on the coach’s ability to perform this task. Coaching is not likely to be successful if the coach is not an expert in training teachers. Added to, a common element of many professional-learning designs that demonstrate gains in teaching and learning is regular teacher collaboration inside a school or among grade levels, sometimes in conjunction with an instructional leader, to develop more effective teaching

ideas and practices. Additionally, some informants supported the idea that teachers should support one another as they progress with their teaching. Others express fervor in favor of the teacher support network that promotes the success of the teaching profession. According to the researcher, every teacher who assists another teacher submits professional development that focuses on its potential to create teacher leaders at the school. This adopts a constructivist philosophy in which educators train other educators, and some high school students serve as ushers at professional development events. The results of this study highlight significant professional development implications that resonate with schools' benefits and highlight the study's potential to foster both teacher and student leadership.

3.1.2. Provides a Helping hand—The informants, who served as the study's interviewers, outlined how the support system assisted the teachers. It is a very clear and helpful way to handle issues with paperwork, classroom management strategies, and any other teacher-related responsibilities appropriately. DeMonte, (2013) stated that administrators in other parts of the educational system can assist teachers in their daily efforts to enhance student learning by ensuring that each teacher gets the resources necessary to provide top-notch instruction. These tools include everything from providing teachers with video equipment so they can record and share their lessons with colleagues to making sure that every district has a team of instructional coaches who are totally committed to supporting high-quality teaching, which is an essential part of professional development. While Hatch et al. (2005) mentioned that teacher leaders are celebrated by their peers as expert educators who offer situational support to other educators in a cooperative and collegial manner rather than as occupants of formal leadership posts. Some of the participants also thought that teachers' ability to provide support

for other teachers would help them succeed and boost student engagement because it is a natural extension of their teaching methods. The academic success of the students was highlighted in the researcher's analysis of the support system. The availability of effective teaching strategies for teachers is mentioned as a benefit of the support system. This serves as the foundation for the students' increasing engagement as a result. The typical college student of today is not the student of today. They are acknowledged as Millennial learners who exhibit a range of thought processes, preferred modes of learning, and multiple intelligences. It is difficult for teachers to adapt and become what their students are becoming as a result. Finally, the respondents have emphasized that through the support system, a win-win situation between the teacher as they have been given a helping hand to work out their workloads effectively while in the part of the students; this has brought light as this denotes boosting their involvement in the learning process.

3.1.3. Boost student involvement—This is where the support system advances. According to Araujo et al. (2014), teachers have an enormous effect on students in the United States. They also show that the determinants of teacher quality are essentially unobserved: Observable characteristics of teachers, such as education, experience, test scores, or salary, are poor predictors of student learning. This is parallel to the study of Archibald et al. (2011), which primarily talks about teachers having a more vital impact on student success than other school features. Assigned teachers who have less experience and who are teaching out of their field or without full certification indicate poor and minority students, which likely negatively influences their ability to produce high levels of student learning. the overall level of teacher effectiveness, a redesign of the systems that recruit, prepare, select, develop, retain, evaluate, and advance, as well as to reduce the variation

Fig. 3. The lived experiences of teachers in the support system

and inequity in teachers’ influence on student learning, the upgrade and compensate teachers addresses the aspect of the teacher support system that is perhaps the most important. Moreover, teachers influence learners’ experiences in the classroom through their instruction and interactions with fellow students. According to contemporary theories of motivation, a positive student-teacher dynamic boosts motivation among learners. To properly engage in communication, one must be able to feel linked to

significant persons in one’s immediate surroundings. If people are in an environment where they feel cared for and important, the likelihood of experiencing intrinsic motivation increases (Ryan Deci, 2009). Figure 3 shows the experiences of the lived experiences support system in understanding mental health and the emergence of the two themes: improve teaching techniques, provide a helping hand, and boost student involvement.

3.2. *The teachers describe the Advantages and Disadvantages of a Support System in Understanding Mental Well-being*—When it comes to the support system among teachers in understanding mental well-being, a variety of ideas are expressed that should be considered and need more comprehension and processing. Participants emphasized that the said support system not only connotes positive impacts or advantages but also looks keenly into the other side, which is the disadvantages, to gain a wider perspective on the teaching practices as familiar to the support system among teachers. Additionally, it aids in developing a deeper understanding of the industry’s current practices and identifies any potential gaps that require special attention and are essential to the teaching

and learning process. In conclusion, the teacher support system affects student outcomes even when teachers are not directly exposed to the same high-quality collaboration. Gains in student achievement are higher in classrooms led by teachers who are better collaborators and in schools with stronger collaborative environments.

3.2.1. *Promote a Successful Learning Process*—To summarize, this is supported by the study of Killion (2015), which states that as a means to improve student achievement, any school and school system leaders and policymakers advocate and support teacher collaboration. The continuation of teacher collaboration, which is to increase student success and teacher performance, was centered on sustained

and perceived as helpful as a productive approach. Teacher collaboration needs leaders who are able to cultivate the capacity to collaborate about instruction, curriculum, students, and assessments, create and support instructional teams to maintain engagement in high-quality collaboration and serve as an advocate of teacher collaboration. It is also invested that in developing a data system that links educator and student data for multiple purposes. Moreover, emphasize on this is as the content focus of professional learning and strong coherence among what students learn, what teachers learn, and school and school system goals are the alignment of teacher performance and student outcomes. Instruction, curriculum, assessment, and student success is what the teacher team ups engrossed on teachers' core responsibilities. When practiced with a focus on instructional strategies, curriculum, and assessment particularly, has benefits for both teachers and students as the outcomes of teacher collaboration. Others added that social support has advantages for people with depression because it can stop negative thought patterns from festering for too long. People who positively impact your life will assist you in finding solutions to your issues and expose you to angles you may not have previously thought of. A new kind of relationship has been shaped into its best form through a support system. The informants considered how important social support is for maintaining good mental, emotional, and physical health. A strong social network is crucial and effective for recovering from depression. Negative thought patterns will lessen with a decreased sense of isolation and an increased sense of belonging and support; this will help the instructional process and the teachers' performance as teachers.

3.2.2. Teacher System of Support—This indicates that the respondents acknowledge a genuine kind of benevolence throughout other teachers and school personnel that was eventually created by the existence of the collaborative

support system. There are tremendous benefits in having a network of supportive relationships, such as having better health, longer lives, and higher well-being. Friends and loved ones can make you more resilient in times of stress, setback, or loss and they can also make the good times even better. This is where they have someone to be at the most backbreaking moments of their lives. Thus, Supportive relationships can bolster you emotionally when you're feeling down or overwhelmed. Friends and loved ones will listen to your fears, hopes, and dreams, and make you feel seen and understood. They can help you think through alternatives and solve problems, and they can distract from your worries when that is what's really needed. In doing all this they provide encouragement and lower your stress and feelings of loneliness. Likewise, knowing people who can provide you with information, advice, guidance, and also tangible support, such as assistance in times of uncertainty, is said to be one of the many practical benefits of having supportive relationships. This feature of social support can be comforting and enhance your feelings of security. However, at times of positivity, we cannot be defiant with the existence of the negativity more particularly the disadvantages. At the end of the informants' remarks, they are also very open with the drawbacks of the said opinions. Some cited that: The respondents also expressed their opinions on a further drawback of the group support system. They support the existence of dependency, where a teacher becomes dependent on other teachers based on the data gathered in a variety of ways, such as when asking for different teaching materials and being reliant when it comes to decision-making, which is a very intricate aspect of being an educator and significantly impacts professionalism. The informants' assertion that they occasionally fail to improve themselves and overcome depression and anxiety and in favor of developing a dependency on others because of the support system is very

Fig. 4. Advantages and Disadvantages of the Support System in Understanding Mental Well-being

illustrative. This problem’s propensity to spread throughout the workplace would result in things like the emergence of poor decision-making and an inability to stand alone.

3.2.3. *Keep Relying on Others*—To sum up, the overly reliant teacher struggles with trust, and he or she has trouble trusting no one but themselves. They struggle with independent

thought and decision-making. The risks becoming your constant companion because he turns to you for support and assistance rather than searching within for the answers. He seems to spend more time hovering by your side or asking you a barrage of questions than he does at his own desk.

This is based on the statement of Jurkovsky and Müller (2018) that if collaboration fails, there are serious flaws, teachers do not plan and assess collaborative instruction, and the approach does not provide the required advantages. The teacher’s role has been identified by Takala and Wickman (2018) as a major barrier to the implementation of co-teaching because it is directly dependent on the other teacher’s decision. This means that a teacher opposed to co-teaching at the school will not support one another. On the other hand, teachers cannot fully dedicate themselves to preparation and thought because they lack the essential time. Most studies found that the most fundamental element affecting the overall efficacy of co-teaching is the shortage of time (Park, 2014; Jurkovsky Müller, 2018). Figure 4 shows the experiences of the

System in Understanding Mental Well-being and the emergence of the two themes: promote successful leaning process, teacher system support and keep relying of others.

3.3. *Educational Insight from the Teachers in Understanding Mental Well-being through Support System*—The researcher discovered during the in-depth interview process that the respondents brought up numerous themes relating to their experiences as teachers in the creation of support systems to enhance teachers’ mental well-being. Every teacher’s greatest asset and the driving force behind the effectiveness of the teaching process is their mental health. In conclusion, a teacher’s teaching abilities are what have contributed most significantly to the success of the teaching process. The researcher noticed that new teachers did not immediately pick up the most essential skills while instruct-

ing. They need a lot of classroom experience to hone their teaching techniques. On the other hand, as a researcher, I emphasized that if teaching practices do not succeed right away, they will take a lot of time. This only means that adequate support must be offered during the required time.

3.3.1. *Enhanced Teaching Methods*—Improved teaching practice is congruent with the statement acclaimed by Simpson, T. (2016), where he highlighted the attributes of the lack of adequate support for teachers based on the continuous increase in attrition rates of teachers within the first five years of entering the profession. It has been concluded that novice teachers leave primarily because of a lack of administrative support, lack of collegial support, student discipline, and poor working conditions. The author also asserted that novice teachers stay in the profession and grow as teachers by means of developing teaching performances whenever administrators support them, provided mentors, and receive professional development focused on classroom management along with identifying challenges and reasons for leaving the teaching profession.

Finally, one of the themes raised by the respondents during the in-depth interview made the researcher realize how important it is not only in the workplace, among coworkers, friends, and family but also that it is something that needs to be given more emphasis because it helps you realize that you are not alone in this society that is constantly demanding. Therefore, this so-called collaborative support system is a significant event that can serve as a stepping stone to develop genuine relationships. By working together, you can overcome challenges, goals, and responsibilities. This genuine relationship can be your outlet for pursuing something you are passionate about and integrating it into your daily life. In terms of teaching, it is indeed one of the noblest professions; however, others consider it to be the most exhausting job

a person could ever have. You not only have to think about how to teach the students efficiently but also need to address issues affecting the parents, community, administration, and many others.

3.3.2. *Developing sincere connections*—This theme is parallel to the study of Mayo Clinic (2010) which cited that successful relationships require give-and-take. A good rule of thumb is to treat your friends as you want to be treated. In other words, be the friend you want to have. Many factors contribute to healthy, happy relationships. This can increase your sense of belonging and purpose, boost your happiness and reduce your stress, improve your self-confidence and self-worth, help you cope with traumas, such as divorce, serious illness, job loss or the death of a loved one, encourage you to change or avoid unhealthy lifestyle habits, such as excessive drinking or lack of exercise. Friends also play a significant role in promoting your overall health. Having a reduced risk of many significant health problems, including depression, high blood pressure, and an unhealthy body mass index, is being portrayed in adults with strong social support. Studies have even found that living longer than their peers with fewer connections is what older adults can get with a rich social life. Cognitive attention on the current environment is particular focused on social stimuli whenever these are present; the physical form, expressions, gestures, voices and behavior of other people in relation to the self. In social settings the brain is constantly engaged not only in ‘watching’ other people but also in interpreting their behavior in goal-directed terms (what they are doing), or emotional terms (how they are feeling). It seems our ability to do so comes about in part through rapid cognitive modelling or simulating of other people’s behaviour as if it were our own. Thus, in effect, by such processes we are able to empathetically interpret and anticipate other people’s behavior by associating the perceived ‘pattern’ of it

Fig. 5. Educational Insight can be drawn from the Teachers in the Development of Support System

with aspects of our own experience (Gallese, Keysers, Rizzolatti, 2019). Figure 4 shows the educational insight that can be drawn from the teachers in developing a support system and the emergence of the two themes: improved teaching practice and developing sincerity.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study. It is followed by implications based on the study’s findings, and future directions were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The main objective of this study was to investigate teachers’ experiences with the support system in understanding their mental well-being. It specifically sought to determine its advantages and disadvantages and describe insights into its significance. The researcher came up with an analysis that revealed teacher’s live experiences regarding the support system, which was classified into three distinct phases: improved teaching practice, providing a helping hand, and boosting student involvement. The researcher concluded that teachers with a robust support system can maximize their professional development for efficient instruction. They are considered thriving professionals since they can carry out their duties and responsibilities and effectively communicate with their students. With the support system’s help, teachers could implement effective teaching practices, increasing student engagement in their studies. This study has demonstrated that, in addition to the school, the community, and the administra-

tors, the students are the ones who gain from the goal of the support system because they become engrossed in their studies as a result of being exposed to effective teaching methods that respect their unique personalities while also addressing their academic needs. Though teachers undergo a support system and divulge that they ensure great experience with it, the researcher also discovered the system’s advantages and disadvantages. The advantages of the collaborative support system embrace three different aspects. The first is to Promote a Successful Learning Process. The achievements in education that have improved and developed students’ learning were the main focus of this. As a result, teachers can teach with such expertise whenever they receive comprehensive support and ultimately help students succeed. The dynamism of teaching practices, strategies, and teaching styles of the teachers was given much attention for delivering instruction to the students, which resulted in student success. However, this was the out-

come of the support system for teachers. Next in line was the teacher system of support. This demonstrates how every teacher's support system creates a similar network. The respondents to this study emphasize that having such a supportive network is one of the best ways to carry out their responsibilities effectively. When they are having a breakdown, knowing that they were highly susceptible to depression and stress, this is where they are inspired and assured to be a successful person. The issue with providing instructional materials is primarily its inadequacy in catering to the number of learners, among other things, which stands out as the disadvantage of the support system and the manifestation of the teachers' dependence. Finally, the insights exhibited by the teachers regarding the support system for teachers in developing teaching practices are associated with two different terms, namely, developing sincere connections and improving teaching practice. Throughout everything stated by the respondents during the interview, even though others specified disadvantages, the support system is undeniably an enormous factor in the success of the field of education. Teachers are also into this kind of system since they are ignited by the success of every bit of the pieces of the educational field, not only for their future self-improvement but also for the eagerness of every student to engage more in learning.

4.2. Implications—The transpiration of the support system to the teachers was an outstanding feature in education. Although the department did not primarily enforce it, it was consequential in improving teaching practices as manifested by the existence of active learning competence of the students as well as the potency of the teachers in the delivery of instruction. Moreover, the support system itself testifies to the ability of teachers to work on helping each other and serve as a helping hand; through this, teachers would eventually express themselves by sharing prowess ideas, ability style

techniques as well and materials, making this an avenue to build strong cordial relationship towards one another. Results indicate that in every workplace an individual belongs to, a support system is a must-have. This enables teachers to become a better version of a professional who upholds the mission, vision, and goals of the school or institution they work for. However, based on the data gathered on the field, some teachers corroborated some impediments in the support system. Teachers argued that they were being provided with materials. However, at the same time, the materials were lacking, which withstand the support system and later affected the teaching and learning process. Further, this was also detrimental to the skills of teachers in terms of being dependent on someone else and confiding the decisions to others. Nonetheless, aside from the disadvantages mentioned earlier, teachers were interested in collaborative support systems for so long as they were equipped with thorough knowledge that would equip them to be ready to involve themselves in the field. They also believed and recognized the system's importance and benefits for both teachers' professional growth and, in the same manner, for the much-improved learning of the students. Finally, the implementation of the collaborative support system may be evaluated to measure its worth in terms of teacher performance and student impact. Promotion and prevention interventions work by identifying the individual, social, and structural determinants of mental health and then intervening to reduce risks, build resilience, and establish supportive environments for mental health. Interventions could be designed for individuals, specific groups, or whole populations. Reshaping the determinants of mental health often requires action beyond the health sector, and so promotion and prevention programs should involve the education, labor, justice, transport, environment, housing, and welfare sectors. The health sector can contribute significantly by embedding

promotion and prevention efforts within health services and advocating, initiating, and, where appropriate, facilitating multisectoral collaboration and coordination.

4.2.1. Future Directions—Various themes, including teaching and learning, human resource development, and governance, spark the development of support systems. To maintain this system's maximum efficiency in education programs across the nation, the following must be given more consideration and emphasis. The National Government may support vast opportunities in the educational sector, particularly the welfare of teachers, who were the key instrument and wheel of education in providing competent individuals to future generations. By emphasizing budget allocation and providing them with training, programs, and other significant

experiences that would improve their teaching performances, the government should support vast opportunities in the educational sector. Instructors should actively cultivate relationships with other teachers and colleagues to stay engaged in studying their craft. This would also serve as a platform for practicing various skills and developing a support system, essential for understanding mental well-being and improving teaching performances. Lastly, the findings of this study would enable future researchers to facilitate research that would involve a support system for teachers to understand mental well-being and improve their teaching performances. This study would also serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

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